

OPTIMIZATION OF THREE PHASE PARTITIONING SYSTEM FOR PURIFICATION OF ACTINIDIN FROM KIWIFRUIT (*ACTINIDIADDELICIOSA*) USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The response surface methodology (RSM) was applied for optimization of the three-phase partitioning (TPP) parameters for purification of milk clotting protease (actinidin) from kiwifruit pulp. A Box-Behnken design was employed to determine the effects of purification parameters namely saturation of ammonium sulfate, volume ratio of tert-butanol to crude extract, and pH value. From RSM optimization study, under the optimized parameters of 42% saturation of ammonium sulfate (w/v), 1.0:0.74 ratio of crude extract to tert-butanol (v/v) and 6.05 pH, the purification fold and activity recovery reached maximum values of 3.16 and 145.37% respectively. As compared to the lower aqueous phase (AP), the recovered protease in the interfacial phase (IP) exhibited milk-clotting activity (MCA). From electrophoretic analysis, the molecular mass was found to be 24 kDa. The substrate zymography revealed the presence of protease in the IP fraction. The findings of this study highlighted that TPP is an efficient technique for fast recovery of actinidin in comparison to other chromatographic techniques.

Keywords: Kiwifruit protease; TPP purification; RSM optimization; SDS-PAGE; zymography

INTRODUCTION

Three phase partitioning (TPP) is non-chromatographic bio separation technique that has overcome the majority of inefficiencies of commonly used separation methods namely supercritical fluid extraction, pressurized liquid extraction, aqueous two-phase system, solvent extraction, as well as chromatographic techniques such as ion exchange chromatography and affinity chromatography. In comparison to other techniques, TPP is an effective, economic, fast, easy to handle, and scalable purification technique (Chew et al., 2018; Gagaoua, 2018; Yan et al., 2018). As an alternative to conventional extraction and purification techniques, the TPP system was first proposed by Tan and Lovrien (1972). Protease is isolated and concentrated in a distinct separate layer between upper butanol phase and bottom aqueous phase when saturated ammonium sulfate salt and tert-butanol solvent are combined (Dennison, 2011). This protocol has been successfully utilized to purify a variety of enzymes such as papain from the peels of papaya (*Caricapapaya*) (Chaiwut et al., 2010), ficin from the latex of *Ficus carica* (Gagaoua et al., 2014), zingibain from the rhizomes of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) (Gagaoua et al., 2016; Gagaoua et al., 2015), cucumisin from the juice of melon (*Cucumis melo*) (Gagaoua et al., 2017), wrightin from the stem of *Wrightia tinctoria* (Rajagopalan & Sukumaran, 2018) and bromelain from the crown of pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) (Gul et al., 2022).

Kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa*) has a high concentration of actinidin (EC 3.4.22.14), cysteine protease, that demonstrated great potential as an effective milk coagulating agent (Grozdanovic et al., 2013). It consists of 220 amino acid residues, having molecular mass of around 24 kDa (Carne & Moore, 1978). The higher ratio of milk coagulating activity to proteolytic activity of kiwifruit extract makes it an appropriate rennet alternative (Nicosia et al., 2022). In addition, its optimal activity at temperatures ranging from 40-42°C and under mild acidic pH conditions make it ideal for the production of cheese (Lo Piero et al., 2011). Actinidin has the ability to hydrolyse the casein fractions in the presence of fat content up to 5% (Puglisi et al., 2012). In casein hydrolysis, the primary substrate for actinidin is β -casein, which is followed by κ -casein. It hydrolyses κ -casein at the Arg₉₇-His₉₈ or Lys₁₁₁-Lys₁₁₂ bonds, compared to chymosin at the Phe₁₀₅-Met₁₀₆ bond (Lo Piero et al., 2011). The cheese made with kiwifruit extract has better nutraceutical quality due to increase in the amount of polyphenols and phytosterols (Serra et al., 2020). Puglisi et al. (2014) utilized an aqueous solution of kiwifruit juice to make mozzarella cheese, and reported a cheese yield of 10.6% with no bitterness.

However, the process of purifying kiwifruit extract is complicated, time-consuming, and necessitates the use of expensive equipment (Puglisi et al., 2014; Mazorra-Manzano et al., 2018). Hence the present work is based on the isolation and purification of milk-clotting protease from kiwifruit with the application of TPP purification technique. The primary objective of this work is to optimize TPP purification conditions via determining the impact of operation parameters namely saturation of ammonium sulfate salt, volume ratio of tert-butanol to crude extract, and extraction pH using RSM (response surface methodology) approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Ripe kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa*) was purchased from the departmental store in Dharan, Nepal. Casein (purified), ammonium sulfate, L-cysteine, bovine serum albumin (BSA) and dialysis membrane were acquired from HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (India). Trichloroacetic acid (TCA), tert-butanol

and protein ladder 26619 were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific Pvt. Ltd. (India). Ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were acquired from Merck, India. All of chemicals used were of the highest purity.

Preparation of crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract

The extraction of kiwifruit protease was performed according to Gagaoua et al. (2017) with slight alterations. Ripe kiwifruit was peeled and cut into pieces, followed by removal of seeds. It was then mixed with 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7) containing L-cysteine (10 mM) and EDTA (2.5 mM) in the ratio of 1:0.2. It was homogenized in a blender, and the obtained homogenate was stirred for 45 min at 4°C. It was then filtered through cheese cloth, and the resulting juice was centrifuged (DLAB D3024R, China) at 7000 rpm (4°C) for 5 min. The supernatant collected was then precipitated up to 65% ammonium sulfate saturation. The obtained pellets were mixed in little amount of phosphate buffer, followed by dialysis overnight at 4°C (MWCO: 12 kDa) with three changes of buffer. The obtained crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract was then purified with TPP (three phase partitioning) system.

TPP of crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract

Crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract was purified by TPP method as derived by Gagaoua et al. (2015). The crude extract (CE) was first saturated with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ salt at 25°C, and then an equal volume of tert-butanol was added. After vortexing, the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature (~25°C) for 45 min. The centrifugation of the mixture was carried out at 4500 rpm for 10 min in cold condition for complete separation into three distinct phases, namely upper butanol, interfacial (middle), and lower aqueous phases. The upper organic phase was discarded, followed by careful separation of other two phases. The interfacial phase was dissolved in a little volume of phosphate buffer. Both phases (dissolved interfacial and aqueous) were overnight dialyzed. The milk clotting activity, caseinolytic activity and protein content were analyzed in both phases. The recovery profile mainly specific activity, purity and recovery were computed for further optimization study.

Response surface methodology (RSM)

Design Expert software (version 13, Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, USA) was used for conducting a three level, three factor Box-Behnken experimental design (Ferreira et al., 2007). The impact of three treatments; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration (w/v), CE to tert-butanol ratio (v/v), and pH was studied on two response variables; purification fold and recovery % of the purified enzyme (Chen et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2011). The optimum range of these treatments was selected from previous study performed by (Maskey & Karki, 2023). The three coded levels -1, 0 and +1 were shown in Table I. A total of 17 experimental runs (comprising 12 factorial and 5 central runs) were performed. Each run was repeated three times. The online $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ calculation tool (www.encorbio.com/protocols/AM-SO4.htm) was utilized for the calculation of salt concentrations.

Table I. Experimental factors and coded levels in RSM design for purification fold and activity recovery optimization of kiwifruit protease

Factors	Symbol	Coded units		
		-1	0	+1
Ammonium sulfate concentration (%)	A	30	40	50
Crude extract to tert-butanol ratio	B	1:0.5	1:0.75	1:1

The responses purification fold and recovery % (Y) for different experimental combinations were related to the coded variables (X_i , $i=1, 2$, and 3) by a second-degree polynomial equation.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_{12} X_1 X_2 + \beta_{13} X_1 X_3 + \beta_{23} X_2 X_3 + \beta_{11} X_1^2 + \beta_{22} X_2^2 + \beta_{33} X_3^2 + \epsilon$$

The coefficients of the polynomial were represented by β_0 (constant), $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ (linear effects); $\beta_{12}, \beta_{13}, \beta_{23}$ (interaction effects); $\beta_{11}, \beta_{22}, \beta_{33}$ (quadratic effects); and ϵ (random error). Data were modelled by multiple regression analysis and the statistical significance of the terms was examined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) for each.

Determination of milk clotting activity

Milk clotting activity (MCA) of the fractions was determined using the method given by International Dairy Federation (IDF, 2007). The reconstituted milk (pH 6.5) in 2 ml vial was incubated at 37°C for 5 min, and 200 μ l protease was then added. At regular 10 s interval, the vial was rotated and checked for any sign of clot. MCA was calculated using Equation (1). One MCA unit is defined as the amount of enzyme that clots reconstituted skim milk (10 ml) in 40 min at 37°C (Berridge, 1952).

$$MCA \left(\frac{U}{ml} \right) = \frac{2400 \times V_s}{T \times V_E} (1)$$

where T = time required for clotting (s); V_s = milk volume (ml); V_E = enzyme volume (ml).

Determination of caseinolytic activity

The determination of caseinolytic activity (CA) of the fractions was conducted following the procedure mentioned by Ladd & Butler (1972) using 1% casein as substrate (w/v) in phosphate buffer (pH 7). After incubation of equal volume (1 ml) of diluted enzyme and casein at 37°C for 30 min, 10% TCA (3 ml) was mixed for the termination of reaction, followed by incubation on ice for 1 h, and centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 min. Absorbance readings of supernatant were taken using double beam spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 60 UV-Vis, US) at 280 nm. CA was calculated using Equation (2). One CA unit is referred to as the quantity of enzyme which releases 1 μ g tyrosine at standard test condition.

$$CA \left(\frac{U}{ml} \right) = \text{Tyrosine } (\mu\text{g}) \times \frac{\text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Volume of enzyme}} \times \frac{\text{Total volume}}{\text{Time of incubation}} (2)$$

Determination of protein

Bradford protein-dye binding method was used to estimate quantitative protein determination of the fractions (Bradford, 1976). The absorbance readings were taken by a double beam spectrophotometer at 595 nm. The protein content was determined by using BSA (bovine serum albumin) standard curve.

SDS-PAGE Analysis

Tricine SDS-PAGE (sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis) was performed using

10% separating gel and 4% stacking gel in SE 400 vertical unit (GE Healthcare)(Schagger, 2006). Briefly, the protein fraction comprising sample buffer (reducing) was heated in water bath at 95°C for 5 min, and 10 µg of protein was loaded in the gel well. Electrophoresis was performed under a fixed voltage of 100 V. Using Coomassie brilliant blue (R-250) in acetic acid, the gel was stained overnight, and then destained twice using acetic acid. The molecular mass of band was determined with the application of GelAnalyzer 19.1 software using prestained protein ladder with a range of 10-250 kDa.

Substrate zymography

In order to validate the existence of protease, zymography using gelatin as a substrate was carried out following the procedure mentioned by Grozdanovic et al. (2013) with minor modifications. Briefly, in the SDS-polyacrylamide gel containing 0.1% gelatin, the separation of protease was performed at non-reducing condition. After renaturation of gel in 2.5% Triton X-100, the gel was immersed in the activation buffer (phosphate buffer containing L-cysteine and EDTA) and incubated at 37°C for 16 h. The gel was then simultaneously stained and destained as previously mentioned. The protease activity was revealed by clear band across the dark background.

Storage stability

For storage stability, the recovered protease was kept for 3 weeks in the refrigerator (4°C) and deep freezer (-20°C). The MCA units (U/ml) were used to express the results (Gagaoua et al., 2017).

Statistical analysis

The analysis of data was carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 27) for ANOVA (analysis of variance) at a 5% significance level. To determine the significant difference among mean values, Tukey's HSD (honestly significant difference) method was implemented. All of the graphs were constructed with Microsoft Excel (2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TPP of crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract

Crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract was isolated and concentrated by utilizing TPP system with application of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ salt and tert-butanol solvent. In general, proteases are concentrated in the interfacial phase (IP) and other impurities are separated in the lower aqueous phase (AP) and upper butanol phase (Gagaoua et al., 2014; Gagaoua et al., 2015; Gagaoua et al., 2017; Gul et al., 2022; Rajagopalan & Sukumaran, 2018). In the current study also, the enzyme showing higher activity was

partitioned in IP fraction [Figure 2(a)], whereas no MCA was demonstrated by AP fraction. Hence the IP fraction was selected to perform the TPP optimization by RSM technique.

Response surface methodology (RSM)

A three level, three factor Box-Behnken Design (BBD) was employed in the optimization of purification factors for RSM studies. In order to determine the highest purification fold and activity recovery %, the ammonium sulfate concentration (30, 40, and 50%), CE to tert-butanol ratio (1.0:0.5, 1.0:0.75, and 1.0:1.0) and pH value (5, 6, and 7) were selected. Table I demonstrates the experimental results.

Table I. Box-Behnken design with experimental values for purification fold and recovery %

Run	A: (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ concentration (%)	B: CE to butanol Ratio	C: pH	Purification fold	Recovery (%)
1	50	1.0:0.5	6	2.420	84.672
2	30	1.0:0.75	7	2.548	93.824
3	40	1.0:0.75	6	3.120	141.584
4	40	1.0:0.5	7	2.450	88.502
5	40	1.0:0.5	5	2.140	64.348
6	40	1.0:0.75	6	3.107	140.225
7	50	1.0:0.75	5	2.785	118.642
8	50	1.0:0.75	7	2.980	132.789
9	50	1.0:1.0	6	2.937	128.335
10	30	1.0:0.5	6	2.108	62.327
11	30	1.0:1.0	6	2.321	77.156
12	40	1.0:0.75	6	3.140	142.429
13	40	1.0:1.0	5	2.560	95.386
14	40	1.0:1.0	7	2.592	98.522
15	30	1.0:0.75	5	2.341	79.868
16	40	1.0:0.75	6	3.096	139.905
17	40	1.0:0.75	6	3.147	143.461

The experimental values were fitted with quadratic second order polynomial regression equations. The equations of both purification fold and recovery % (in terms of coded values) are shown in (3) and (4) respectively. Statistical significance of these equations was analyzed by ANOVA for quadratic model of responses (Table 2 and 3).

$$\text{Purification fold} = 3.12 + 0.2255A + 0.1615B + 0.0930C + 0.0760AB - 0.0030AC - 0.0695BC - 0.2238A^2 - 0.4518B^2 - 0.2347C^2$$

(3)

$$\text{Activity recovery (\%)} = 142.52 + 18.91A + 12.44B + 6.92C + 7.21AB + 0.0477AC - 5.25BC - 16.90A^2 - 36.49B^2 - 18.34C^2$$

(4)

Where A, B, and C are coded values of (NH₄)₂SO₄ concentration, CE to butanol ratio, and pH respectively. A², B², C², AB, BC, and AC are model terms.

Table 2. ANOVA for purification fold quadratic model

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Model	2.16	9	0.2399	272.17	< 0.0001
A	0.4068	1	0.4068	461.53	< 0.0001
B	0.2087	1	0.2087	236.73	< 0.0001
C	0.0692	1	0.0692	78.50	< 0.0001
AB	0.0231	1	0.0231	26.21	0.0014
AC	0.0000	1	0.0000	0.0408	0.8456
BC	0.0193	1	0.0193	21.92	0.0023
A ²	0.2108	1	0.2108	239.15	< 0.0001
B ²	0.8593	1	0.8593	974.87	< 0.0001
C ²	0.2320	1	0.2320	263.25	< 0.0001
Residual	0.0062	7	0.0009		
Lack of Fit	0.0043	3	0.0014	3.10	0.1512
Pure Error	0.0019	4	0.0005		
Cor Total	2.17	16			

From the analysis of purification fold regression model (Table 2), (NH₄)₂SO₄ concentration (A), CE to tert-butanol ratio (B), and pH (C) exhibited significant (p<0.05) positive impact on purification fold at a 95% confidence level. AC (interaction term of A and C) showed non-significant (p>0.05) negative effect, while AB (interaction term of A and B) showed significant (p<0.05) positive impact, and BC (interaction term of B and C) as well as A², B², and C² (quadratic terms) demonstrated significant (p<0.05) negative impact on purification fold. This regression model is significant as evidenced by a model p-value less than 0.0001, while the insignificant (p>0.05) lack of fit indicated well fitted model. The obtained result was also verified with R² value. The value of predicted R² was found to be 0.9668, which is in reasonably consistent with adjusted R² value 0.9935. Hence, this regression model could be implemented for analysis as well as prediction of the purification fold.

Table 3. ANOVA for activity recovery quadratic model

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Model	13826.78	9	1536.31	218.67	< 0.0001
A	2860.06	1	2860.06	407.09	< 0.0001
B	1238.78	1	1238.78	176.32	< 0.0001
C	383.55	1	383.55	54.59	0.0002
AB	207.85	1	207.85	29.58	0.0010
AC	0.0091	1	0.0091	0.0013	0.9723
BC	110.44	1	110.44	15.72	0.0054
A ²	1203.07	1	1203.07	171.24	< 0.0001
B ²	5607.87	1	5607.87	798.20	< 0.0001
C ²	1415.70	1	1415.70	201.50	< 0.0001
Residual	49.18	7	7.03		
Lack of Fit	40.30	3	13.43	6.05	0.0574
Pure Error	8.88	4	2.22		
Cor Total	13875.96	16			

From activity recovery regression model analysis (Table 3), A, B and C exhibited significant (p<0.05) positive impact on recovery at a 95% confidence level. Similarly, AB revealed significant (p>0.05) positive impact. But AC showed non-significant (p>0.05) positive impact whereas BC as well as A², B² and C² demonstrated significant (p<0.05) negative effect on yield. A model p-value of less than

0.0001 indicated significant regression model, while insignificant ($p>0.05$) lack of fit revealed well fitted model. Predicted R^2 value was 0.9525, which is in reasonably consistent with adjusted R^2 value 0.9919. Therefore, using this regression model, the recovery % could be analysed and predicted.

The interactive effects of each two factors used to identify the optimal level for maximum purification fold as well as recovery % in the response surface plots are demonstrated in Figure 1. The responses at centre point exhibited higher purification fold and recovery in comparison to those at factorial point. Kumar et al. (2011) and Chen et al. (2022) reported similar trend. Hence, both purification fold and recovery increased at around 40% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration, 1.0:0.75 CE to tert-butanol ratio, and pH 6. Since the elliptical curve shape was exhibited by all interactions in this design, the interrelated impacts of variables assisted to predict optimal levels for maximum purification fold and activity recovery %.

Optimization

Numerical optimization method was used to identify the optimal conditions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration, CE to tert-butanol ratio and pH value for maximum purification fold and recovery (Table 4).

Table 4. Different parameters for RSM optimization

Parameters	Goal	Lower limit	Upper limit
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration (% w/v)	in range	30	50
CE to tert-butanol ratio (v/v)	in range	1.0:0.5	1.0:1.0
pH	in range	5	7
Purification fold	maximize	2.108	3.147
Activity recovery (%)	maximize	62.327	143.461

The optimal conditions were found to be 41.983% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration, 1.0:0.738 CE to tert-butanol ratio and 6.052 pH, comprising the desirability 1. Under these conditions, the purification fold and activity recovery were 3.153 and 144.178% respectively.

Verification of model

In order to validate the adequacy of regression model equations, 3 experimental runs were performed. The results of the confirmatory tests are shown in Table 5. The experimental values were very near to the predicted values, demonstrating that this regression model is precise enough to predict the optimal value. Hence, 42% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration, 1.0:0.74 CE to tert-butanol ratio, and pH 6.05 were chosen for overall purification of kiwifruit protease.

Table 5. Response predicted and experimental values

Response	Optimum conditions			Predicted mean value	Experimental mean value
	Salt concentration	Ratio	pH		
Purification fold	42	1.0:0.74	6.05	3.2	3.2
Recovery (%)	42	1.0:0.74	6.05	144.324	145.373

Overall purification profile

The purification profile of TPP purified kiwifruit protease is summarized in Table 6. The RSM optimized TPP of crude extract resulted in enhanced purification fold and activity recovery of 3.16

and 145.37% respectively in IP fraction, when compared to AP. Table 7 also demonstrates the comparison of purification techniques for kiwifruit protease. The purification of kiwifruit protease by TPP system exhibited high degree of purification as well as recovery value (>100%), when compared to chromatographic techniques. Hence, simultaneous activation of enzyme with higher purification fold and recovery values was achieved by TPP approach (Rather & Gupta, 2013). The reduced interfering substances during pre-dialysis and enzyme activation during ammonium sulfate precipitation might account for enhanced purification fold, whereas the synergistic effect between salt concentration and solvent volume under optimized condition might be the reason for higher recovery % (Rajagopalan & Sukumaran, 2018). Similar results on TPP purification of plant proteases were reported by (Gagaoua et al., 2015;Gagaoua et al., 2017;Hafid et al., 2020 and Gul et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Response surface plots showing the impact of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ concentration, CE to tert-butanol ratio, and pH on purification fold and activity recovery %.

Table 6. Overall purification profile of kiwifruit protease

Fractions ¹	Total activity (U)	Total protein (mg)	Specific activity (U/mg)	Purification fold	Recovery (%)
CE	64.98	2.91	22.33	1 ^a *	100 ^a
IP	92.46	1.34	70.5	3.16 ^b	145.37 ^b
AP	2.86	0.41	6.98	0.31 ^c	4.4 ^c

Note.¹42% concentration of (NH₄)₂SO₄ was mixed to CE and pH 6.05 was adjusted. The tert-butanol was added at ratio of 1.0:0.74. After 45 min, upper butanol phase was discarded while IP and lower AP were separately collected to determine MCA, CA, and protein content. AP exhibited no MCA, while IP showing higher enzyme activity was selected for further study. * Different alphabets represent significantly different (p<0.05).

Table 7. Comparison of purification methods for kiwifruit protease

Source	Purification method	MW (kDa)	Purification fold	Recovery (%)	Ref.
<i>Actinidia deliciosa</i> Chev. Abbot	60% ammonium sulfate precipitation DEAE-anion exchange chromatography	27	2.42	22.43	Dhiman et al. (2021)
<i>Actinidia chinensis</i>	50% ammonium sulfate precipitation DEAE-cellulose column chromatography	24	2.4	8.7	Lo Piero et al. (2011)
<i>Actinidia deliciosa</i>	Three phase partitioning	24	3.16	145.37	Present study

Tricine SDS-PAGE and Zymography

Under reducing condition, Tricine SDS-PAGE analysis of TPP fractions showed that the IP fraction had molecular mass of 24 kDa [Figure 2(b)]. Similar molecular mass of actinidin (~24 kDa) was reported by Carne & Moore (1978), Nieuwenhuizen et al. (2007) and Lo Piero et al. (2011). Mahdian Dehkordi et al. (2022) reported 29 kDa molecular weight of actinidin. The relative protein content and diversity of kiwifruit cultivars could be the cause for variation in molecular mass of actinidin (Maddumage et al., 2013). Furthermore, the Figure 2(c) demonstrated the proteolytic property of the IP fraction by digesting the gelatin at the similar position of molecular mass, as evidenced by clear band.

Figure 2. TPP and determination of molecular mass of purified kiwifruit protease. (a) TPP result demonstrated in eppendorf tube showing partitioned actinidin in the IP fraction. (b) Tricine SDS-PAGE (10% separating gel and 4% stacking gel): Lane L, Ladder; Lane 1, crude dialyzed kiwifruit extract; Lane 2, IP with 24 kDa molecular mass; and Lane 3, AP. (c) Gelatin zymography: clear band indicated the hydrolysis of gelatin by actinidin.

CONCLUSION

RSM was utilized to optimize the TPP parameters during the extraction and purification of kiwifruit protease. The optimized TPP conditions of 42% saturation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (w/v), 1.0:0.74 ratio of crude extract to tert-butanol (v/v), and 6.05 pH revealed increased purification fold and recovery of 3.16 and 145.37% respectively. The recovered protease was concentrated in the interfacial phase, and its molecular weight was observed 24 kDa from the electrophoretic analysis. Hence TPP could be an effective and economic non-chromatographic fast separation technique for the purification of actinidin.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there do not have any conflict of interest.

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